

Conductometric studies and thermodynamics of dissociation and association of cerium and thorium laurate in mixed organic solvents

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Abstract : The conductometric studies of the solutions of cerium and thorium laurate in the mixture of 70/30 benzene-methanol (v/v) has been carried out at 25–40 °C in order to determine the CMC, limiting molar conductance, dissociation constant and thermodynamic parameters for both dissociation and association processes. The results show that these soaps behave as a weak electrolyte in benzene-methanol and Debye-Huckel-Onsager's equation is not applicable to the solutions of these soaps and micellization process is favored over the dissociation process.

Keywords : Critical micellar concentration, solvation, phase separation model, micellization process.

Introduction

In the recent years, metal soaps have found extensive applications in different industries as well as in academic field. Their appreciable solubility in organic solvents, stability and chemical reactivity, together with their volatility and availability¹⁻⁶ at a reasonable cost make them potentially useful for its applications in various fields such as softeners, plasticizers, lubricants, chemical thickener in greases, catalysts in chemical industries, medicines, emulsifiers, waterproofing agents, in paints and coating and processing aid in rubber industry. Sato *et al.*⁷ manufactured the cosmetic gels containing metal soaps. Narita *et al.*⁸ manufactured metal soaps for block for copier and fax machines. Metal soaps are also very interesting for their uses as polymer stabilizers or optical polymer fibers⁹⁻¹¹.

Varma *et al.*¹² measured the conductance of aqueous solutions of calcium salts of lower fatty acids at different temperatures. Kishore *et al.*¹³ investigated the conductance, micellization and dissociation behaviour of terbium soaps in the mixture of benzene and methanol. Topallar *et al.*¹⁴ investigated micellization, thermodynamics of dissociation of chromium soaps in different solvents. Metal soap with elements of lanthanide series was synthesized for the first time by Mishra *et al.*¹⁵. Skrylev *et al.*¹⁶ studied the formation of lanthanum soaps by the reaction of lantha-

num chloride with corresponding potassium soaps conductometrically. Mehrotra *et al.*¹⁷ prepared the lanthanide soaps of saturated and unsaturated fatty acids and determined the thermodynamic parameters in non-aqueous media.

The comparative study on micellization and electrolytic behaviour of dysprosium soaps in methanol were carried out by Shukla *et al.*¹⁸. The present paper deals with the study of conductance of solutions of cerium and thorium laurate in a mixture of 70/30 benzene-methanol (v/v) at different temperatures. The results have been used to find out the nature of these soaps in non-aqueous medium and to determine thermodynamics of dissociation and association processes.

Results and discussion

The increase in specific conductance with the increase in soap concentration and temperature is attributed to the dissociation of soaps in mixed organic solvent, in dilute solutions, as well as the formation of micelles at higher soap concentration. Critical micellar concentration (CMC) of cerium and thorium laurate in benzene-methanol mixture were determined from the plots of specific conductance, k vs soap concentration, C (Fig. 1) which are characterized by an intersection of two straight lines at CMC. Below this concentration, these solutions exhibit properties similar to those of ordinary electrolytes, but above

Fig. 1. Variation of specific conductance with concentration of cerium laurate.

this concentration the properties differ from normal electrolytes indicating that micelle formation takes place at definite soap concentration.

The process of micellization was assumed to occur when the energy released as a result of aggregation of hydrocarbon chains of the monomers was sufficient to overcome and to balance the decrease in entropy accompanying aggregation. Since the kinetic energy of the monomer was higher at higher temperature, CMC will also higher (Table 1).

Table 1. Values of CMC, limiting molar conductance and dissociation constant

Soaps	Temp. (°C)			
	25	30	35	40
CMC × 10 ⁻³ (g mol l ⁻¹)				
Cerium laurate	3.25	4.25	5.25	6.00
Thorium laurate	3.75	4.75	5.70	6.25
Limiting molar conductance (μ ₀)				
Cerium laurate	8.50	9.70	10.50	11.70
Thorium laurate	7.30	8.30	9.40	10.30
Dissociation constant (K _D × 10 ⁻⁵)				
Cerium laurate	9.28	10.96	13.53	15.30
Thorium laurate	6.21	8.45	11.85	14.19

The molar conductance (μ) of the solutions of cerium and thorium laurate decreases with increase in soap concentration. This decrease is attributed to the combined

effects of the decreasing mobility due to ionic atmosphere, solvation of ions and formation of micelles. The plots of molar conductance (μ) vs square root of soap concentration, C^{1/2} were not linear which indicates that these soaps behaves as weak electrolytes in dilute non-aqueous solutions and Debye-Huckel-Onsager's¹⁹ equation is not applicable to these soap solutions. Their dissociation can be derived from the following expression :

$$\mu^2 C^2 = \frac{K_D \mu_0^3}{4\mu} - \frac{K_D \mu_0^2}{4} \quad (1)$$

where K_D is dissociation constant.

The values of limiting molar conductance, μ₀, dissociation constant, K_D have been obtained from the slope,

$$\left[\frac{K_D \mu_0^3}{4\mu} \right] \text{ and intercept } \left[\frac{-K_D \mu_0^2}{4} \right] \text{ of the linear plots}$$

of μ²C² vs 1/μ below the CMC for dilute soap solutions and are recorded in Table 1.

The values of dissociation constant, K_D were approximately constant in dilute solutions but exhibit a drift with increasing soap concentration. This drift in the values at higher concentrations may partly be due to the degree of dissociation being not exactly equal to the conductance ratio, but it is more due to the activity coefficients of ions not being equal to unity. Simple Debye-Huckel activity equation may fall at higher soap concentration. The value

for limiting molar conductance and dissociation constant increases with increase in temperature. On comparison it was found that the values of limiting molar conductance and dissociation constant of cerium laurate are higher than the values for thorium laurate.

Various thermodynamic parameters for dissociation and association process have been calculated. The heat of dissociation ΔH_D is represented by the following expression :

$$\log K_D = -\Delta H_D/2.303RT + C \quad (2)$$

The heat of dissociation, ΔH_D for cerium and thorium laurate in benzene-methanol mixture have been obtained from the slope of linear plots of $\log K_D$ vs $1/T$. The negative value of heat of dissociation, ΔH_D for cerium and thorium laurate was found to be 4.87 and 9.75 kJ mol⁻¹ respectively. The results of heat of dissociation indicate that the dissociation of these soaps is exothermic in nature. On comparison it was found that the value of ΔH_D for cerium laurate is greater than thorium laurate.

The values of the change in free energy, ΔG_D per mole of monomer and standard entropy change, $T\Delta S_D$ was evaluated for the dissociation process by using the relationship :

$$\Delta G_D = -RT \ln K_D \quad (3)$$

$$T\Delta S_D = \Delta H_D - \Delta G_D \quad (4)$$

The calculated values of ΔG_D and $T\Delta S_D$ are recorded in Table 2. The positive value for the change in free energy for thorium laurate is higher than cerium laurate.

In the aggregation process counter ions are bound together to form a micelles, the standard free energy of micelle formation, ΔG_M can be expressed by equation :

$$\Delta G_M = (2 - \beta) RT \ln X_{CMC} \quad (5)$$

where X_{CMC} is defined as the CMC expressed in terms of

mole fractions and is explained by the relationship :

$$X_{CMC} = n_s/n_s + n_o \quad (6)$$

where n_s and n_o are the number of moles of soap and solvent, respectively. Since the number of moles of free soaps is small as compared to number of moles of solvent, $n_s + n_o$ is nearly equal to n_o and X_{CMC} can be calculated as n_s/n_o , and β is calculated from the specific conductance vs concentration plots and is equal to the slope of this plot above CMC divided by the slope of this plot below CMC.

The negative value of free energy of micellization decreases with increasing temperature of the soap (Table 2). The negative free energy of micellization of cerium laurate was higher than the thorium laurate.

The standard enthalpy change of micellization per mole of monomer for the phase separation model²⁰⁻²² ΔH_M was calculated by the relationship :

$$\partial(\ln X_{CMC})/T = -\Delta H_M/2RT^2 \quad (7)$$

or

$$\ln X_{CMC} = \Delta H_M/2RT + C \quad (8)$$

The values of ΔH_M of cerium and thorium laurate has been obtained from the slope of the linear plots of $\ln X_{CMC}$ vs $1/T$ and were found to be 40.98 and 36.11 kJ mol⁻¹ respectively. The positive enthalpy $\Delta H_M > 0$ signifies that the association process of these soaps in benzene-methanol mixture is endothermic in nature. The comparison of results indicated that the association process for cerium laurate was more endothermic than thorium laurate.

The values of standard entropy change per mole of monomer, $T\Delta S_M$ for micellization process is calculated as

$$T\Delta S_M = \Delta H_M - \Delta G_M \quad (9)$$

Table 2. Thermodynamic parameters of dissociation and association of cerium and thorium laurates in a mixture of 70/30 benzene-methanol (v/v) at various temperatures

Temp. (°C)	Cerium laurate				Thorium laurate			
	ΔG_D	$-T\Delta S_D$	$-\Delta G_M$	$T\Delta S_M$ (KJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔG_D	$-T\Delta S_D$	$-\Delta G_M$	$T\Delta S_M$
25	23.03	27.90	25.93	66.91	24.02	33.77	23.10	59.21
30	22.99	27.86	24.63	65.61	23.64	33.39	21.83	57.94
35	22.90	27.77	23.99	64.97	23.16	32.91	18.63	54.74
40	22.89	27.76	20.20	61.18	23.07	32.82	16.47	52.58

The value of $T\Delta S_M$ decreases with increase in temperature. On comparison this value for cerium laurate is higher than thorium laurate.

The micellization of cerium and thorium laurate in a mixture of 70/30 benzene-methanol (v/v) is consistent with $\Delta H_M > 0$, $\Delta G_M < 0$, $T\Delta S_M > 0$ where as dissociation of these soaps accord with $\Delta H_D < 0$, $\Delta G_D > 0$, $T\Delta S_D < 0$ (Table 2). The negative values of enthalpy change of dissociation may compensate for the unfavorable change in free energy and entropy of dissociation process. The reason for unfavorable entropy change may be due to the ion solvent interactions. The negative values of free energy, ΔG_M and positive values of entropy, $T\Delta S_M$ favor micellization and can make up for the unfavorable enthalpy change $\Delta H_M > 0$ for the association process.

It may therefore concluded that cerium and thorium laurate behave as weak electrolyte in a mixture of 70/30 benzene-methanol (v/v) and the values of CMC increases with increase in temperature and size of metal ions. A careful analysis of thermodynamic parameters indicates that the micellization process is favored over the dissociation process and the exothermicity of cerium laurate was greater than thorium laurate.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The cerium and thorium laurate were prepared by the direct metathesis of corresponding potassium soaps by pouring a slight stoichiometric excess of aqueous metal salt solution into the clear dispersion at raised temperature with vigorous stirring. The purity of soaps was checked by determination of their melting points, IR spectra and elemental analysis. The conductivity measurements of solutions of cerium and thorium laurate in mixture of 70/30 benzene-methanol (v/v) were made with a "Systronic Conductivity Bridge 305" (SR No. 993) and a dipping type conductivity cell (cell constant 1) with a platinized electrodes. The cell constant was determined by using standard solutions of potassium chloride and the accuracy was checked by repeating the measurements with fresh solutions several times. The specific conductance is expressed in mhos cm^{-1} , respectively.

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